

Electrical Insulation for Nb₃Sn Superconducting Cables

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From Discovery of Superconductivity to Large-Scale Particle Accelerators

- **Superconductivity** is a property of certain materials that exhibit **zero electrical resistance** below a critical temperature (T_c). Enables current flow without power loss due to **absence of the Joule effect**.
- **Discovered in 1911** at Leiden University (Netherlands) by **Heike Kamerlingh Onnes**. He was awarded the 1913 Nobel Prize in Physics.
- In the **80's** the **first large-scale applications** of superconductivity began to appear: **Tevatron** particle accelerator built at Fermilab (USA). 774 x 4.3T dipoles 6-m long used to bend the particles in the ring.
- In **2006** the **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)** was commissioned at CERN (Switzerland). The largest existing particle accelerator with a 27-km circumference.

HL-LHC and Beyond... Future Circular Collider (FCC) at CERN

- The next step for CERN is the **High-Luminosity upgrade (HL-LHC)** aiming at increasing the collisions thus the view of rare phenomena, precision of the measurements and opening the way to new discoveries.
- **For the first time, Nb₃Sn magnet will be installed in an accelerator.** 30 powerful quadrupoles installed around ATLAS and CMS detectors
- **HL-LHC will start operation in 2030.**

- Scientific community is discussing about a 90.7-km-Circumference **Future Circular Collider (FCC)** at CERN developed with a 2-stage approach: FCC-ee from the **mid-2040s** and FCC-hh from **the 2070s.**

- It calls for development of **Nb₃Sn accelerator dipole magnets with 14 T operational field** with focus on **sustainability, cost and large-scale production.** This is the scope of **High Field Magnet (HFM) program**

Nb₃Sn Coil Insulation Systems

- During construction and operation, superconducting magnets as well as their insulation systems are exposed to **cryogenic temperature** (1.9 K), **high radiation levels** (1 – 30 MGy) and **mechanical loads**, especially during assembly (~100 MPa).
- A robust electrical insulation is key to assure reliability and performance of the magnets.
- Within HFM program, an R&D work package is devoted to the development of **enhance electrical insulation systems** for Nb₃Sn coil.

What is demanded to an insulation system for HFM?

- To have **high dielectric strength (voltage withstand ~ 2 kV)**
- To have **good mechanical properties** (at each stage of magnet manufacturing and operation, loads ~100 MPa)
- To have a **high radiation hardness (up to 30 MGy)**
- To be as thin as reasonably achievable (in consideration of all other requirements)
- To possibly have **good thermal properties** (high heat capacitance and conductivity)
- Others...

Manufacturing a Nb₃Sn coil (1/2)

COIL WINDING

The cable is wound around a pole mounted on a steel mandrel. For long coils (> 8 m) the winding process is carried out by an automatic winding machine.

REACTION HEAT TREATMENT

The “reaction” process is required to create the intermetallic compound Nb₃Sn. Coil heated to about 650-700 °C in vacuum or inert gas (argon) atmosphere for roughly 50 hours.

Topic #2

INSULATION

The insulation is constituted by a glass fibers braided onto the Nb₃Sn cable.

Topic #1

Manufacturing a Nb₃Sn coil (2/2)

MQXFB coil inside the impregnation tank CERN

VACUUM IMPREGNATION

After reaction the Nb₃Sn becomes brittle. Carefull handling is required. The coil is vacuum impregnated with epoxy to create a monoholitic component and provide dielectric insulation.

Topic #3

The following steps include the assembly of the coils in a coil-pack, assembly of the yoke, welding, insertion in the cryostat, testing and installation...

Cable Insulation

Cable Insulation

- Fiber is **braided** directly around the Rutherford-type conductor
- Typically, **S2 glass** is chosen for the higher mechanical properties and thermal stability compared other glass fibers
- Conductor **insulation thickness 0.145 ± 0.05 mm**

Control of Insulation thickness

- The **target insulation thickness** is achieved tuning the braiding pitch.
- Control of insulation thickness** is extremely important because tight tolerances required during the magnet assembly.

$$p = LVDT_{insulated}(\sigma_t) - LVDT_{bare}(\sigma_t) = t_{insulation} * 20$$

- Quality control** of each insulated Unit Length (UL) is measured with “**10-stack**”. Difference of consecutive measurements of a stack of 10 conductors with braided sleeve and without:

10 STACK MEASUREMENTS: MQXFB CABLES

Insulation thickness for different braiding pitches

Insulation thickness for different UL (E. Fernandez Mora)

Braided Insulation Layout

- **Fibre volume fraction V_f** determine final properties of the insulation dielectric strength, mechanical strength, thermal conductivity and Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE)
- Typical **target of fibre volume fraction is > 50%**
- Two types of braiding layout: **single** (filament $\varnothing=9\ \mu\text{m}$) and **double sleeve** (filament $\varnothing=5\ \mu\text{m}$). Both types display a **$V_f \sim 60\%$**

Braided Insulation Layout

Double sleeve has the advantage of having smaller epoxy volumes therefore less stored strain energy (accumulated during cooldown 300 K \rightarrow 4K). Epoxy cracks when stored strain energy is greater than work of fracture

Fiber desizing

Nb₃Sn reaction treatment: Desizing effect

- The insulated coil is heated to about 650-700 °C in vacuum or inert gas (argon) atmosphere for roughly 50 hours. This is the reaction cycle of Nb₃Sn.
- The sizing undergoes a **pyrolysis** leaving **conductive products** on the fibers.
- Conductive products **impact the dielectric strength** of the insulation. The effect is less dramatic at cryogenic temperatures

Superconducting coil before and after heat treatment

J. Osuna et al, "Advanced Composite Insulation Systems in Nb₃Sn Superconducting Magnets for Accelerators: Electrical Characterization of Laminates at Cryogenic Temperatures", accepted for ICEC/ICMC 2024

Thermal and Plasma Desizing

Desizing methods:

- **Thermal desizing** consists of injecting oxygen to burn off the sizing during the reaction treatment
- **Plasma desizing** consists of using a plasma torch to burn off the sizing before the cable is wound

Plasma treatment on reacted glass fibres

Typical Nb₃Sn reaction cycle

Epoxy systems

Impregnation systems

Current status on impregnation systems:

- In most cases, **epoxies** are used for impregnation
- Among them, two families of hardeners can be used: **amine and anhydride**
- Other chemicals can be added to tailor processing and end properties such as accelerator or flexibiliser

Desired properties for processing:

- **Low viscosity / long pot life** (coils are 8 to 15 m long)
- Low shrinkage during curing and low exothermic behaviour
- **Low curing temperature** to reduce thermal stresses

Desired end properties:

- **High dielectric strength**
- **Good mechanical properties**
- Thermal shock resistance
- **High radiation hardness (dose depends on where the magnet is installed in the accelerator – few MGy to 30 MGy)**
- Lowest possible CTE mismatch with coil constituents

Anhydride hardener

Flexibiliser

Fracture toughness of epoxies

Fracture toughness of different epoxies at room temperature and 77 K:

- Overall, the **fracture toughness of anhydride epoxies is lower than amine epoxies, especially at low temperatures**
- To toughen CTD101K epoxy, a flexibiliser DY040 was added (10 and 20 w%), leading to a toughness increased by 50 % at 77 K

➔ Epoxy resin + flexibiliser

Fracture toughness test sample

Influence of the chemistry on the radiation hardness

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) study of irradiated epoxies:

- **The epoxies with anhydride hardeners are more resistant to radiation** e.g. CTD101K, MSUT (MY740) and CEA mix (CY 192-1) compared to epoxies using amine- based hardeners (Mix 61 and MY750)

CTD101K vs CTD101K + DY040 (POLAB mix):

- DMA (up to 38 MGy) and 3-point bending (up to 20 MGy) studies did not reveal significant change of radiation hardness between the two systems
- **DY040 can be used to increase fracture toughness without impacting the radiation hardness**

Influence of irradiation environment and temperature

DMA study of irradiated epoxies in air, inert gas or liquid helium:

- Strong different efficiency for producing radiation damage, depending on the irradiation temperature
- More cross-linking and less chain scission in inert gas
- **Cross-linking is nearly completely suppressed in liquid helium**
- The temperature effect on chain-scission is materials dependent

To predict the dose limits of organic materials in superconducting magnets, **irradiations need to be performed at cold**

New set up for cold irradiation test campaign under construction at CERN

Electrical Performance

Insulation Quality and Electrical Performance

- For High Field Magnets expected **voltages to ground and between turns** range approximately around **1.5 kV** and **100 V** respectively.
- The **quality** of the insulation is assessed **by voltage withstand test** and **partial discharge (PD)**.
- Turn-to-Turn insulation withstand >2.5 kVdc before and after controlled cold thermal cycles down to 77 K (LN₂)
- **Partial Discharges (PD)** are localized breakdowns. It can appear in voids, cracks, across the insulation surfaces and in air (corona).
- **PDs can reveal the presence of defects** in the insulation that may develop in failures if subjected to repeated thermal cycles or mechanical loads

Representative samples of turn-to-turn insulation (HV 10-stacks)

Example of carking on coil after exposure to liquid Helium (right); delamination and cavities on insulated cable. SMC coils (Courtesy of J.C. Perez)

Partial Discharges

- The size and shape of a defect can be estimated by **Paschen Law of gases**, the PD inception voltage (**PDIV**)* and the interpretation of the Phase-Resolved PD (**PRPD**) pattern.
- Defect free Turn-to-Turn insulation are **PD free up to ~ 8 kV**. It is possible to assume that **cavities**, if present, **<~ 6 μm**.
- PDIV** occurs on some samples around **4 kV**. Possible **flat cavity or delamination** of approximately **10 μm** (or spherical voids ~25 μm).
- PD inception voltage of insulation that underwent **five thermal cycles in LN2** was on the range of **2.5 kV**. Possible flat cavity or delamination of approximately **15 μm** (or spherical voids ~30 μm).

PDIV 7.7 kV; PRPD attributed to micro-voids

PDIV 4 kV; PRPD attributed to delamination

PDIV 2.5 kV; PRPD attributed to delamination

*voltages expressed in peak values

PD data from D. Polvani - internal document (EDMS)

Conclusions and perspectives

- **Robust electrical insulation** is essential for the reliability of Nb₃Sn superconducting magnets for particle accelerators
- **Control of the braiding process** is necessary to meet tight magnet construction tolerances and insulation quality.
- **Desizing techniques** (thermal, plasma) are promising in improving dielectric performance, but scale-up and validation in coils are ongoing.
- An epoxy system tailored with flexibiliser can **enhance fracture toughness** at cryogenic temperature without compromising radiation hardness – critical for long-term performance.
- **Partial Discharge (PD)** testing is a valuable diagnostic tool to assess insulation quality and detect early signs of degradation due to thermal-mechanical induced stresses.

Thank you for your attention